

1 **Hypoxia in a mouse model of stroke.**

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6 Stroke is a leading cause of death. We studied oxygen deprivation, hypoxia, at the transcriptional level in
7 the middle cerebral artery occlusion model, an animal model of stroke. We observed activation of hypoxia
8 inducible factors *Hif3a* and *Hif1A*. Oxygen sensor *Egln3* was induced while *Egln1* induction was very
9 weak. *P4hb*, a hypoxia target gene, was activated to an extent greater than 95% of the transcriptome.
10 The hypoxic response was concomitant with indicators of tissue damage - induction of *Timp1* and *Timp4*.
11 Cerebral infarction features a robust hypoxic response accompanied by tissue damage.
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